

Eliciting the voice of autistic girls in research: A systematic review protocol

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There is a rising interest in how autism may uniquely impact girls, as they are often under-diagnosed, misdiagnosed, or late diagnosed. Autistic advocates have been critical of how research involving autistic people has been conducted. This has led to an increase in the use of participatory research methods and increased value placed on the inclusion of first-hand accounts of lived experience. With these two pertinent considerations for future autism research in mind, the current study seeks to catalogue methods which have been used to elicit the voice of autistic girls (under 18) in research. This systematic review will, in addition to collating previous methods used, endeavour to 1) explore how/why these methods have been chosen based on author declaration; 2) form the basis of consultation with a cohort of autistic girls (12-17) for their feedback on these methods and 3) lead to recommendations for future researchers who wish to include autistic girls in their research as participants. This project is currently at the title and abstract screening phase (Round 1) This systematic review protocol is outlined in detail, beginning with inclusion criteria for studies screened, search terms chosen, inter-rater procedures implemented throughout the project and our plan for data extraction. Justifications for our choice of quality appraisal tool and approach to missing data during data extraction will be highlighted. Our conclusion section discusses what publications we anticipate rising from the current research and highlights our broader aim of encouraging future authors engage directly with autistic participants.

Keywords: Autism; Autistic Girls; Systematic Review; Research Protocol; Participatory Methods.

Highlights

- There is a rising interest in and need for participatory methods in autism research, with particular attention being paid to cohorts of participants within the Autism Spectrum who may be further marginalized by age and gender.
- This paper outlines a protocol for a systematic review that is currently underway. This paper sets out to examine methods used to elicit the voice of autistic girls.
- This systematic review is part of a wider research endeavor, and is the first study of two which, together, will form the basis of guideline recommendations for future researchers who wish to include autistic girls as participants.

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Introduction

Increased contention surrounds how autistic people are included in autism research (Gowen et al., 2019), partly due to the criticism of autistic advocates who feel objectified and misrepresented (Botha and Cage, 2022). This has resulted in several efforts to promote inclusive practices in research, including 1) participatory research approaches (den Houting *et al.*, 2021), 2) person-oriented methodologies (Cascio, Weiss and Racine, 2020) and 3) meaningful inclusion of autistic voices (Milton, Mills and Pellicano, 2014). While these developments are an improvement, a wider issue remains – disabled people may be further marginalised by additional factors such as age (autistic *children*) and gender (autistic *girls and women*), remaining underrepresented in autism research (D’Mello *et al.*, 2022; Mullally *et al.*, 2024). This is pertinent given the increased ratio diagnosis in girls (Loomes, Hull and Mandy, 2017) with late and misdiagnosis resulting in a lack of research representation.

Advocates argue that research is predominantly conducted by and with non-autistic people (Holt *et al.*, 2022) which perpetuates the exclusion of autistic participants. These proxies are usually parents/caregivers, educators, or healthcare professionals (Mullally *et al.*, 2024). This means that despite there being work exploring the lived experiences of autistic children, findings are derived from second-hand sources rather than directly engaging autistic children themselves. An additional axis of marginalization to consider when representing autistic people is gender. There is consensus that despite developments in our understanding of autism, research remains persistently male dominated (D’Mello *et al.*, 2022). The resulting real-world impact is that autistic girls/women remain under/late/mis-diagnosed (Gesí *et al.*, 2021) and research remains biased.

Conceptualization of the current study involved investigating the space in research where these axes meet – people who are 1) autistic, 2) children, and 3) female.

Through initial literature screenings it was found that previous works exist which address either 1) involving autistic children in research or 2) the unique phenotype of ‘female’ autism (Hull, Petrides and Mandy, 2020). However, the pitfalls of current autism research persist – researchers fail to directly engage autistic girls. Nevertheless, there are a minority of studies which do elicit the views, experiences, thoughts, etc. (hereafter referred to as ‘voice’) of autistic girls. This minority is the focus of the current review. A systematic review will be used to identify 1) what methods are used to elicit autistic girl’s voices in research and 2) what evidence, if any, authors provide to defend their choice of methods used

and/or any accommodations they made for engaging this specific cohort. We intend to present a summary of findings to a Young Person's Advisory Group (YPAG) of autistic teenage girls to elicit their response, opinions, etc., and ask what changes or additions they would include.

Initial screening uncovered a particularly relevant study by Fayette and Bond (2018). Their systematic review synthesized literature pertaining to qualitative methods that have been used to elicit the views of autistic young people about their educational experiences. Our review seeks to replicate their methodology to synthesise relevant literature with the following focus: 1) research which either solely includes autistic girls or pieces which have an extractable cohort of girls and 2) highlights methods by which autistic girls share their views in research contexts rather than educational experiences, as was the focus of Fayette and Bond (2018).

Research Aims

- 1) To identify methods used to elicit autistic adolescent girl's (aged 12-17) opinions, feelings, and accounts (referred to as 'voice') in research.
- 2) To present a summary of findings to autistic adolescent girls and ask for their insights, opinions and suggestions regarding these findings.
- 3) To form best-practice recommendations for researchers hoping to involve autistic girls in research which seeks to elicit their voice.

Research Questions

Systematic Review

1. What research methods are used to elicit the views of autistic adolescent girls?
2. What evidence, if any, is given to support the use of methods chosen to elicit the voice of autistic adolescent girls?

Young Person's Advisory Group (YPAG) Consultation

3. What insight can be gained from directly engaging autistic girls regarding the findings of this review?

Proposed Methods

Overview

This systematic review has been pre-registered (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/8M96Q>) via Open Science Framework (OSF) (Foster and Deardorff, 2017). Comprehensive literature searches were conducted on the 2nd of July 2025 and imported to Covidence systematic review management system (Kellermeyer, Harnke and Knight, 2018) by the 4th of July 2025. This review is currently in the Title and Abstract (Round 1) screening phase.

Screening and Inclusion Criteria

All database search results will be screened using the criteria outlined below:

- 1) The publication must be an original article that has been published in a peer reviewed journal.
- 2) All articles must be published in English
- 3) The searches will be limited to include studies published on or after January 2013. This covers the time since the last major update of the DSM criteria for Autism (Boshoff et al., 2024).
- 4) The study must have included at least one autistic girl (whose data, in the case of mixed sex studies, could be independently extracted from that of participants of other genders).
- 5) The study design may be either quantitative, qualitative, mixed-methods or multiple methods. Case studies as well as group designs may be included.
- 6) The study must elicit the voice of autistic girls to share thoughts, feelings and accounts of their own experience(s) of being autistic. These studies may include the voices of proxies, provided the autistic voice(s) can be extracted independently.

Other reviews will be excluded from the current study, though any which are returned during searches will be subject to reference harvesting.

Search Procedure

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) (Page *et al.*, 2021) framework, a 27-item guideline for reporting on systematic literature reviews, will be employed for write-up of any articles resulting from this study. As

Fayette and Bond (2018) had a similar goal of gathering studies which had elicited autistic voice, their selection of databases (Applied Social Science Index and Abstract, Web of Science, PsychInfo and Education Resources Information Centre) is replicated with the exception of one, Google Scholar. As Fayette and Bond did not share their procedure for collecting and screening studies via Google Scholar, it was decided that this source of articles would be substituted with an alternative, Scopus. Scopus was chosen given its position within social science research as one of the largest and most comprehensive databases. Additionally, it is considered comparable and complimentary to Web of Science (Burnham, 2006) in terms of relevant literature encompassed.

Search Strings

Three distinct categories of search terms were chosen for this study – terms related to 1) autism, 2) eliciting voice, and 3) age & gender (combined so as not to inadvertently exclude studies with autistic women which include a cohort of girls under 18; or studies which include autistic children, but not girls specifically). Search terms were decided based on those used by Fayette and Bond (2018) and in consultation with the project supervisors, LG and RS. The final search string was: Autism OR Autistic OR ASD OR ASC OR "Autism Spectrum Disorder" OR "Autism Spectrum Condition" OR Asperger* OR "Aspergers Syndrome" OR Autis* OR "Pervasive Development*" OR PDD OR PDD-NOS OR "On the Spectrum" AND Interview* OR "Focus Group*" OR Qualitative OR Speak* OR Opinion* OR Thought* OR Feeling* OR Voice* OR Experience* OR Lived-Experience* OR Perspective* OR Attitude* OR Belie* OR View* OR Consult* AND Girl* OR Wom* OR Woman OR Women OR "Gender Difference*" OR Female* OR Teenager* OR Adolescen* OR "Young Person" OR "Young People" OR Child*.

Databases were searched simultaneously by the first author and a second, independent screener to ensure the searches were replicable. Once both raters verified that each search returned the same results, the results from each database were exported to Covidence (see Figure 1). While other reviews (e.g., systematic reviews, meta-analyses, etc) will be excluded from analysis in the current study, reviews will be saved to allow for reference harvesting. A list of reviews used for reference harvesting will be presented in an updated version of the methodology, at a future point.

Figure 1: PRISMA Search Flow Diagram

Quality Appraisal

The Critical Appraisal Skills Programme checklists (CASP, 2023) are a set of critical appraisal tools for assessing the quality of research. These checklists have been chosen due to ease of use and applicability after being piloted. As the individual checklists are tailored to be used with varying study designs, it was decided that these were the most appropriate appraisal tool given the potential for our final list of included studies to include a variety of research designs. These checklists include tailored items which are relevant to respective study designs. No studies will be excluded as a result of quality appraisal, rather, quality appraisal scores are being recorded for author consideration during analysis – e.g. in case there are observable commonalities in low vs high quality studies which may impact recommendations arising from this review, etc.

Data Extraction

A data extraction form will be designed and piloted on a subset (30%) of studies. This form will be altered as needed for full data extraction. For each of the included studies, data pertaining to the following four categories will be extracted: Study Identity; Design, Demographics of Participants, Methodology Used, and Findings.

- 1) Study Identity: title, ID (author, year), year conducted/date of publication, age range of participants, where the study was conducted, ethnic information.
- 2) Design: aim of study, qualitative/quantitative/mixed/multiple methods, who conducted the study (researcher/educator/etc), sample size, what accommodations were used/offered.
- 3) Demographics of Participants: gender, age, ethnicity, diagnosis/level of disability/co-occurring conditions, cognitive capacity.
- 4) Methods: data collection method (interview, focus group, survey, etc.), commentary and/or justification given for methods implemented.

Reliability

Title and abstract screening (Round 1) will be independently conducted by the first author and a second screener. An inter-rater reliability score (Cohen's Kappa) will be calculated for reporting and/or as a potential indication, in the case of low inter-rater reliability, that search inclusion criteria must be refined and Round 1 repeated. The Cohen's Kappa score controls for chance in determining the level of agreement between two raters of

categorical (qualitative) data. A high level of inter-rater reliability is crucial for mitigating the risk of subjective interpretations and biases impacting upon the screening process. Once this is complete, both screeners will meet to resolve any conflicts. If a resolution cannot be reached in any case, the project supervisors (LG and RS) will be consulted for a final decision. Once this process is complete, both screeners will proceed to full-text screening (Round 2) of all included studies. As in the previous round, screeners will blindly indicate which articles will proceed to data extraction. Any conflicts will be discussed and resolved as described in Round 1 and an additional inter-rater reliability score generated.

As there is no formal scoring system for the CASP Checklists, it is up to the appraiser to determine whether the item responses amount to reflect a study of high, medium or low quality. To mitigate the subjectivity this allows, an inter-rater will also implement the relevant checklists on all or a subset of the included studies, depending on the final number of studies. As with the screening rounds, a Cohen's Kappa will be calculated, conflicts will be resolved amongst the screeners and if any disagreements persist, the project supervisors (LG and RS) will be consulted.

As was the case during the screening and appraisal phases, an inter-rater will be using the finalized data extraction form on all or a subset of the studies (depending on the final number included) to ensure reliable data extraction. In any case where data cannot be extracted (such as missing data for ethnicity), this will be considered as relevant and valuable to the analysis of findings and will be discussed as such.

Limitations

Due to the power imbalance between researcher and participant, autistic children in particular may feel that there are 'correct' answers to questions posed (Winstone *et al.*, 2014), which may cloud the authenticity of responses. In our review, we will be cognisant and seek to identify steps to mitigate this which were taken by previous authors; and during our YPAG participants will be assured that there are no correct/expected responses and that we are seeking their own, genuine feedback. Additionally, there exists a trend within autism research of findings being interpreted via the lens of diagnostic criteria (Milton, 2012; McLaughlin and Rafferty, 2014). This could be a pitfall that arises from the epistemological positions of the researcher. The current authors are mindful of this and, in the spirit of moving away from the medical model of disability, will be cognisant during data analysis and reporting this potential bias. Non-speaking or minimally verbal autistic children are also often excluded

from research and so it is expected that 1) the findings of the review may be biased towards verbal autistic perspectives and 2) the design of our YPAG will also be representative of this subset of the autistic community, as we will encourage the use of assistive technology such as AAC devices to facilitate their participation where possible. This study is limited to reviewing articles published in English only, meaning it may be inherently biased towards Western cultural and academic norms. Finally, our search strategy only allows for the inclusion of peer-reviewed articles, meaning a blanket exclusion of dissertations and other grey literature.

Conclusions

Once data extraction is completed, the primary aim of this review is to compile a list of all methods that have been used to elicit autistic girl's voices in research. For the systematic review itself, these findings will be analysed and considered in relation to best-practice guidelines for including autistic girls in research as, to the best of the current authors knowledge, no such guidelines exist specifically for participants who are both autistic *and* girls. Furthermore, authors justification or lack, thereof, of their choice of methodology with respect to participants who are autistic girls will be explored. Finally, our discussion will explore the relevance of any missing data within both the context of individual study quality/reporting, and the wider lens of what that missing data may mean or represent in a wider research context – e.g. findings may be limited by missing data and/or not applicable to *all* autistic girls.

In addition to this systematic review, ethical approval has been secured to bring our findings to a YPAG of autistic girls for consideration. While the authors may speculate as to the appropriateness of methods within the review, our intent is to present this list neutrally to the YPAG for their non-primed feedback on individual methods. We seek these consultations with the hope that qualitative, autistic girl's contributions may enhance and deepen understandings of their needs as research participants. These sessions will also be used to gain additional context for why certain methods may be preferred/non-preferred and why; and what additional methods/accommodations/considerations autistic girls feel may be relevant or beneficial for facilitating their voice in research. This opportunity will also be taken to consult with autistic girls on what their priorities for future research with autistic girls would be. Our hope is that through these studies, we may highlight the pertinence of

consulting with experts by lived experience and encourage future researchers to employ participatory methods wherever possible.

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